

Aircraft Operator Safety Case for Managing Fume Risk

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ABSTRACT

This paper is intended to offer a modelled approach for an aircraft operator to present the possible arguments for the management of risks of fume contamination of the cockpit or passenger cabin during operational flights of their aircraft. The primary approach in this paper is the Bowtie hazard analysis tool and the risk assessment matrix.

INTRODUCTION

Operating a public transport air transport organization carries corporate responsibilities and liabilities for senior management, in particular the accountable manager. In the current public transport regulatory environment there is a defined requirement for a safety management system, part of which includes a need to identify the risks and associated hazards that drive those risks. The accountable manager should be able to display an understanding of the risks that the organization faces, and the means to reduce or manage those risks to acceptable levels; this accountability cannot be delegated, albeit the actions to manage those risks can be assigned to others within the organization.

Cabin air includes by design the use of tapped engine air for both pressurization and cabin climate management. This tapped engine air contains particulates that can be

harmful to the passengers and crew, although generally in minor amounts that are either tolerable or of limited individual exposure. However, it is now recognized that there is a demonstrable risk that needs enhanced management, beyond those levels originally perceived. This paper sets out to enhance the understanding of this risk for aircraft operators through the use of a specific hazard analysis that could aid the air operator in meeting their corporate responsibilities.

Safety case

The safety case proposed herein is a simplified document that attempts to make fume risk management understandable to aircraft operators, flight crews and maintenance engineers, as these are the individuals that manage this risk and its associated hazards. The core element of this safety case is based upon a Bowtie hazard analysis and a single risk assessment. For aircraft operators, this risk and hazard combination forms part of their overall safety case or defined means of managing significant risks through the safety management system. However, for the propose of this presentation, it is focused on the single risk of fume penetration of the occupied spaces of the aircraft. Hazard analysis is a modelled approach that is not specific to any aircraft type or aircraft operator, but forms a generic document that could form the basis for any operator fume risk/hazard analysis.

Fume contamination may not be considered a major risk to the aircraft operator in their risk profile, but it should be assessed as it has the potential to affect the wellbeing of flight crews and passengers. In extreme cases it could result in fatalities and threaten the aircraft's ability to be safely landed.

The aircraft operator accountable manager is accountable for the management of risks. The level of risk is not the key issue, only that it exists and threatens the health of the occupants of the pressurized aircraft. That risk now needs to be acknowledged and managed by the individual operators. If not appropriately addressed, it can leave aircraft operators exposed to future challenges and potential liabilities. It is no longer possible to deny knowledge of this hazard any longer as

finally the evidence supports this potential problem.

Hazard analysis

The single Bowtie analysis identifies the hazard (the source of energy that needs to be controlled), the top event (the first point of release of the hazard) and a

number of threats that may cause control of the hazard to be partially or fully lost. Failure to contain through multiple threat controls, or alternately recover from the loss of control is also defined in the hazard analysis as a series of potentially worsening consequences (Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1 – Bowties Without Controls Depicted

Analysis components

1. Hazard: Contaminated Bleed Air
2. Top Event: Toxic fumes from aircraft pressurization and conditioning systems in cockpit and cabin.
3. Threats:
 - T1—Inadequate aviation regulatory oversight for air contamination. (Regulatory-based problem that does not currently require any monitoring or oversight at the point of design and build or during continuing operations).
 - T2—Occupational health and safety regulations not applied or enforced for air crew and passengers in relation to air contamination. (Regulatory-based problem where existing rules are not applied in aviation due to exclusions of regulators who might otherwise be actively pursuing this issue).
 - T3—Oils reaching the gas path used at high temperatures where toxins are released. (Design-based problem where oil manufacturers set temperature limits for the safe use that are exceeded as the potential effect is not considered).
 - T4—Unfiltered air drawn from the engine and APU systems for pressurization and cabin conditioning. (Design-based problem which is the common practice of almost all pressurized aircraft currently in use as the potential problems of contamination was not generally considered relevant).
 - T5—Limited loss of oil across engine labyrinth and carbon seals is common and a function of the design and is exacerbated by seal wear and other factors. (Design-based problem that is a fact of design of the seals but was not generally considered for its potential to contaminate the occupied space air).
 - T6—Engineering defect resolution does not adequately consider toxic fume release into the gas path used for pressurization. (Maintenance-based problem that has not been well understood or addressed by the maintenance community, or indeed called for by the manufacturers or regulators).

Top event

The left-hand part of a Bowtie hazard analysis is constructed with a series of control barriers that define the means to maintain control of all the threats and keep the operation in equilibrium. The Top Event (also known as the Hazardous Event) is at the center of the Bowtie and depicts the first point of loss of control, but at a point where control may be regained. The right-hand side of the Bowtie is designed to lay out the recovery measures needed to regain control of the hazard. However, they don't always work which would result in an unwanted outcome that can be minor or major in its results, these are known as consequences.

Consequences

The consequences of loss of control of the hazard may vary, but from a risk assessment consideration they are normally assessed as the worst creditable outcome or the most likely outcome. For the accountable manager it makes sense to document the worst credible consequence that the company may be held responsible for and if it is a lesser event at least the company should have been prepared.

CONCLUSIONS

This presentation is designed to assist aircraft operators with reinforcing their safety program by correctly identifying and subsequently managing a previously little understood hazard in normal operations. I set out to demonstrate the possible threats and controls needed to manage the hazard and avoid potential consequences. This is not necessarily a comprehensive answer to the problem and therefore each operator should consider the risks and hazards applicable to their company. Operators consider this identified risk for which they may well be held accountable in the future. Detailed copies of the generic safety case could be made available to aircraft operators that want to address the potential risks.